

INCREASED EDUCATIONAL ROLE AND MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR THE TEACHER

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Annotation: The article examines the role and place of the teachers in improving the quality of the education system, global changes in the field of education in the country, the specifics of the teaching profession and modern tasks and requirements set for teachers.

Key words: education, upbringing, work of a teacher, features, development, criteria.

The role and role of the teacher in the upbringing of a harmonious generation that meets modern demand is incomparable. He has a central place in the process of education and upbringing and always remains so. A teacher (educator) is a person with special education, professional training, high moral qualities in pedagogical, psychological and specialty areas, operating in educational institutions.

Our great ancestor, Sultan Alisher Navoi of the ghazal Estate, describes the hard work of the teacher: "his work cannot be done by man, not by man, not by man, but by the giant. One strong man was powerless to keep a young boy, and he would teach a bunch of children Science and decency, what he would do to it.

The famous educator, founder of the Uzbek school Abdullah Avlani also gives a special place to express views on the personality of the teacher and his activities. Alloma points out that the role of the teacher in the development of a child's health is unparalleled by the fact that parents play a unique role. That is, the formation of the mental abilities of children is "a sacred task that rests on the attention of teachers, is assigned to their conscience", "depends on the strength, elegance, breadth of their thought, the upbringing of the teacher".

The famous educator Yan Amos Komensky notes that "teaching is a very proud profession that stands higher than any profession on Earth." Since the image of a teacher is images, it emphasizes that it is advisable to have the following qualities in his person: a conscientious, workaholic, patient, moral, lover of his own work, treating students as their fathers, instilling in them an enthusiasm for knowledge, a person who follows students behind him and has his own beliefs.

Along with the fact that the teacher is a huge responsible, broad - minded and growing knowledge holder, modernity is its mandatory quality, the demand for knowledge, the more strict demand for it. That is, if knowledge is not coordinated to this time, its relevance will decrease.

From the early days of our independence, there was a special focus on educating young people, which has been raised to the level of statewide politics, while the focus on this issue has now been further strengthened.

Taking into account the fact that the training of personnel in accordance with the needs of society and the requirements of today goes to resources, the amount of funds allocated to the educational system in our republic from the state budget is increasing from year to year.

Particular attention is paid to ensuring the continuity of education, the creation of an opportunity to make extensive use of the information technology of each student, the world experience through the excellent study of foreign languages.

In our country, we can see that special attention is paid to the educational system not only in the increase in the amount spent, but also in the creation and further improvement of its legal and regulatory framework.

A special place is occupied by the law on education, which is aimed at reforming the educational system. Without creating an effective educational system, it is difficult to imagine the implementation of the set tasks for reforming society. It is for this reason that priority will undoubtedly be given to this area, which is to lay the groundwork for its further development.

The training of knowledgeable, cultured, spiritually high specialist personnel, the emergence of human potential in every way depends on the mentors, their organization and teaching of the educational process with knowledge. Mentoring is an honorable, but incredibly hard work. It is known that pedagogical labor is distinguished from other types of Labor by a number of its features:

- It is aimed at teaching and educating a person who is the greatest miracle of nature;
- It embodies in itself a whole case the personality of a specialist, educator, administrator and researcher;
- The teacher must be able to speak and think. That is the specificity of the teaching profession, work, skills. When teaching, the process of thinking, thinking and speaking is added. There will be no opportunity to think first and then speak;
- The managerial activity of the teacher is fundamentally different from other areas. He makes the only decision in any problem situation.

The purpose of the pedagogical process is not only to educate the student-student, organize training, but also to determine his teaching methods and the system of all relations in them. In the implementation of such complex, painstaking work, a modern teacher should have the following qualities:

- **Vol:** This is the most difficult, but necessary condition for existence as a full-fledged person.
- **To admit his mistakes:** Only one who does nothing makes a mistake.
- **Development:** If the pace of the world has not changed for several generations, now it is developing at such a rapid pace that the teacher also needs to understand what modern students live with.

The famous ancient Greek philosopher Plato said that " if the poor man is a bad master, then the state will not lose anything much from this – only the people will dress worse. But if the youth educator performs his duties badly, then a category of ignorant, ignorant, ignorant and stupid will arise in the country".

Even in our country, serious requirements are imposed on teaching personnel based on the need of the present day in relation to their spiritual image, mental potential and professional skills.

To give knowledge at the level of modern demand, first of all, the teacher himself must have such knowledge. This is the first criterion. The idea that "you can teach someone other than you don't know" has long prevailed among American Scientists. (The Uzbek folk proverb " read what the Mullah knew " expresses it beautifully.) But Rudolf Dreycur believes that knowing the subject is not enough. It is also necessary to understand the content and

essence of complex, difficult thoughts, ideas, know how to turn them into an understandable topic.

The second criterion for the teacher is pedagogical knowledge. It includes the level of study of areas related to knowledge, the ability to set educational goals and other goals, lesson planning (design), determining the methods used, determining the time distribution, setting problem questions, developing procedures for the work to be done, and preparing masala-exercises, tests and other tasks. The third criterion is a teaching, teaching skill, which consists in how, with the help of strategies, methods, methods, assignments, it is possible to attract students to the study of science.

Taking into account the changes in the global scale in our republic and the fact that all issues go to the personnel in many ways, attention was paid to developing countries and, based on our experience, teachers, their knowledge and skills play a key role in improving the quality of the educational system, meeting the requirements of the time and the need to determine its level,

A number of regulatory documents were adopted, which stipulated that the qualification requirements for those engaged in pedagogical activity should be clear and understandable, make them self-assess and, accordingly, ensure regular work on them. President Of Our Republic Sh. Mirziyoev's decree PD-4947 of February 7, 2017 "on the strategy of action for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" further increases the responsibility of teachers. It is important not only to convey the essence of the decree to the minds of readers and students, but also to ensure its implementation and direct to act along the way.

It can be seen that each teacher, as specified in the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on education", should be the owner of relevant information about his subjects, the owner of high professional training and high moral qualities. In addition to being a means of giving deep knowledge, the training organized by a teacher who has mastered the art of teaching serves as a mirror that shows the prosperity of an independent Uzbekistan, its confidence in tomorrow, what the intelligence and labor of our people are capable of, what it is necessary to do to become a worthy citizen and faithful builder of society.

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